

SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART II. LEAD MONO-PROPIONATO AND MONO-FORMATO COMPLEXES

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The composition of the complex formed between Pb^{2+} and propionate ions has been found to be $(PbProp.)^+$ from a study of the equilibrium hydrogen-ion concentrations in mixtures of equimolecular lead nitrate and propionic acid solutions by "Job's method of continued variation", using the increase of hydrogen-ion concentration as a new index. Proceeding similarly, the composition of the complex formed between Pb^{2+} and formate ions has been found to be $(PbFor.)^+$.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium $PbProp.^+ \rightleftharpoons Pb^{2+} + Prop.^-$ has been found out as 4.57×10^{-3} at $28-30^\circ$ by the direct application of "law of mass action", taking into account the activity coefficients of the individual ions, calculated from the ionic strength of the solution mixture of lead nitrate and propionic acid, employing the "Debye-Hückel limiting law". Proceeding similarly, the thermodynamic dissociation constant K for the equilibrium $(PbFor.)^+ \rightleftharpoons Pb^{2+} + For.^-$ has been found to be 182.0×10^{-3} at $26-30^\circ$. The first step of dissociation of lead formate in aqueous solution, viz. $PbFor.^+ \rightleftharpoons (PbFor.)^+ + For.^-$ has been suggested as nearly complete, and the reasons have been advanced.

Following the same procedure adopted for lead acetate complex, described in Part I of this series (this issue, p. 269) the thermodynamic dissociation constants for the equilibria, $(Pb Prop.)^+ \rightleftharpoons Pb^{2+} + Prop.^-$ and $(PbFor.)^+ \rightleftharpoons Pb^{2+} + For.^-$,

$$K = \frac{a_{Pb^{2+}} a_{Prop.^-}}{a_{PbProp.^+}} = \frac{c_{Pb^{2+}} c_{Prop.^-}}{c_{PbProp.^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{Pb^{2+}} f_{Prop.^-}}{f_{PbProp.^+}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$K = \frac{a_{Pb^{2+}} a_{For.^-}}{a_{PbFor.^+}} = \frac{c_{Pb^{2+}} c_{For.^-}}{c_{PbFor.^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{Pb^{2+}} f_{For.^-}}{f_{PbFor.^+}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

(where $Prop.^-$ stands for $C_2H_5COO^-$ and $For.^-$ stands for $HC(=O)O^-$)

have been found out from the determination of p_H of solution mixtures containing a volume '1-x' of lead nitrate and 'x' of propionic acid or formic acid, x varying between 0.1 and 0.9, and both parent solutions being at the same concentration, 'C'. The composition of the complex formed has been determined as in the case of lead acetate complex in Part I (*loc. cit.*) by the application of "Job's method of continued variation" using the increase, 'Y', of the hydrogen-ion concentration in the mixture, over the sum of hydrogen-ion concentrations of the parent solutions, at the same dilution, as the index property*. From the curves representing Y-x plots, it has been found that the maximum value of 'Y' corresponds to the reacting proportion 1:1 for lead nitrate and propionic acid or formic acid. This shows that under the condition of the experiment, the following equilibrium alone is most prominent, and the formation of higher complexes, e.g. $PbProp._2$, $PbProp._3$ etc.

* In the present case, however, the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture of '1-x' c.c. of lead nitrate solution at concentration 'C' with 'x' c.c. of water is very small, and has therefore been neglected in calculating the value of 'Y'.

or PbFor_3 , PbFor_2^- etc. as the case may be, is negligible. The reaction can therefore be written in the case of propionic acid as

or, in the case of formic acid as

assuming complete dissociation of lead nitrate and nitric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The lead nitrate used was of the reagent quality (E. Merck, Darmstadt) and propionic acid (B.D.H., Lab. reagent) was distilled under atmospheric pressure with anhydrous calcium chloride, and the fraction coming exactly at 141° was employed. The formic acid used was of Analar quality. All solutions were prepared with conductivity water.

Preparation of stock solutions of lead nitrate and propionic acid/formic acid, both of concentration 'C', was made exactly like lead acetate complex in Part I (vide Experimental). After keeping the mixtures as shown in Tables I and III, in a closed room for 3 hours in the case of propionic acid mixtures and 4 hours in the case of formic acid mixtures, the p_H values were determined from E.M.F. (E) measurement, using the formula noted below, at room temperature (t°) with the help of a Leeds and Northrup K_2 -type potentiometer, using saturated calomel and quinhydrone electrodes, bridged by a saturated KCl solution (Kohlthoff and Laitinen, "p_H and Electro-titration", 2nd ed., p. 92, John Wiley).

$$p_H = \frac{0.4552 - 0.00009(t - 25) - E}{0.0591 + 0.0002(t - 25)}$$

The E.M.F. reading for each solution was repeated in duplicate in all cases, and in many cases in triplicate, using each time a solution mixture independently prepared from the same stock solutions, and sometimes from different stock solutions, and in all cases, the readings gave p_H values agreeing within ± 0.01 unit.

FIG. 1

FIG. 3

TABLE I

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.			Concentration of parent solutions			
	HProp.	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Water.	M/2; C=0.5; $\rho=1$; Temp.=30°.		M/5; C=0.2; $\rho=1$; Temp.=28°.	
				μ .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).	μ .	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).
0.1	9	1	...	2.14	49.53	2.486	18.4
	9	...	1	2.64		2.838	
0.2	8	2	...	2.07	63.73	2.402	26.14
	8	...	2	2.67		2.87	
0.3	7	3	...	2.02	75.55	2.37	30.07
	7	...	3	2.70		2.90	
0.4	6	4	...	2.00	81.38	2.343	33.91
	6	...	4	2.73		2.94	
0.45	5.5	4.5	...	1.985	85.92	2.335	35.15
	5.5	...	4.5	2.755		2.955	
0.50	5	5	...	1.985	86.90	2.335	35.52
	5	...	5	2.78		2.97	
0.55	4.5	5.5	...	2.00	84.15	2.343	35.30
	4.5	...	5.5	2.80		2.996	
0.60	4	6	...	2.01	82.76	2.36	34.14
	4	...	6	2.825		3.022	
0.65	3.5	6.5	...	2.027	80.17	2.377	33.17
	3.5	...	6.5	2.86		3.055	
0.70	3	7	...	2.035	79.38	2.394	32.31
	3	...	7	2.89		3.094	
0.75	2.5	7.5	...	2.065	74.62	2.424	30.12
	2.5	...	7.5	2.94		3.122	
0.80	2	8	...	2.107	68.61	2.466	27.59
	2	...	8.0	3.02		3.18	
0.90	1	9	...	2.235	51.53	2.586	21.47
	1	...	9	3.173		3.35	

TABLE II

(The symbol used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part I of the series *loc. cit.*.)

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.		Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HProp.	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	M/2; C=0.5; $\rho=1$; Temp.=30°.	M/5; C=0.2; $\rho=1$; Temp.=28°.		
			μ .	$K \times 10^3$.	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.
0.1	9	1	0.1444	0.83	0.0582	1.49
0.2	8	2	0.2927	0.51	0.1171	1.04
0.3	7	3	0.4414	0.28	0.1766	0.80
0.4	6	4	0.5908	0.18	0.2367	0.57
0.45	5.5	4.5	0.6653	0.13	0.2660	0.48
0.50	5	5	0.7403	0.11	0.2950	0.42
0.55	4.5	5.5	0.8156	0.095	0.3260	0.38
0.60	4	6	0.8907	0.078	0.3561	0.35
0.65	3.5	6.5	0.9662	0.065*	0.3862	0.31
0.70	3	7	1.041	0.050*	0.4163	0.27
0.75	2.5	7.5	1.117	0.042*	0.4465	0.25
0.80	2	8	1.192	0.035*	0.4769	0.22
0.90	1	9	1.344	0.020*	0.5376	0.15

N.B. The ionisation constant of propionic acid at the temperature of the experiment (28-30°) has been taken to be $K_a = 1.33 \times 10^{-5}$ ("The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions" by Harned and Owen, 2nd ed., p. 580).

* These points could not be shown in Fig. 2, but they also fall on the straight line.

FIG. 2

FIG. 4

TABLE III

(HFor. stands for formic acid)

1-2.	Solution mixtures in c.c.			Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HFor.	Pb(NO) ₂	Water.	M/5; C=0.2; p=1; Temp.=26°. p _H .	Increase in (H ⁺) (Y × 10 ⁴).	M/3; C=0.33; p=1; Temp.=30°. p _H .	Increase in (H ⁺) (Y × 10 ⁴).
0.1	9	1	...	2.31	2.21	2.208	4.26
	9	...	1	2.33	...	2.239	...
0.2	8	2	...	2.275	8.42	2.148	16.04
	8	...	2	2.35	...	2.259	...
0.3	7	3	...	2.22	18.57	2.078	31.08
	7	...	3	2.38	...	2.280	...
0.4	6	4	...	2.20	24.20	2.055	39.01
	6	...	4	2.41	...	2.309	...
0.45	5.5	4.5	...	2.21	24.51	...	...
	5.5	...	4.5	2.43	...	...	...
0.50	5	5	...	2.22	24.78	2.048	44.46
	5	...	5	2.45	...	2.346	...
0.55	4.5	5.5	...	2.236	24.97	...	...
	4.5	...	5.5	2.48	...	...	...
0.60	4	6.0	...	2.245	25.27	2.074	44.06
	4	...	6	2.50	...	2.395	...
0.65	3.5	6.5	...	2.275	24.25	...	...
	3.5	...	6.5	2.54	...	...	...
0.70	3	7.0	...	2.286	25.46	2.111	42.46
	3	...	7	2.58	...	2.456	...
0.75	2.5	7.5	...	2.32	23.87	...	...
	2.5	...	7.5	2.62	...	...	...
0.80	2	8.0	...	2.354	22.	2.169	40.47
	2	...	8	2.67	...	2.564	...
0.90	1	9.0	...	2.464	20.01	2.259	36.11
	1	...	9	2.843	...	2.722	...

TABLE I.

(The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part I of the series, *loc. cit.*.)

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.		Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HFor.	Pb(NO ₃) ₂ .	M/5; C=0.2; $\phi=1$; Temp.=26°. μ .	K × 10 ³ .	M/3; C=0.33; $\phi=1$; Temp.=30°. μ .	K × 10 ³ .
**0.10	9	1				
0.20	8	2	0.1250	15.62	0.2036	57.7*
0.30	7	3	0.1818	13.16	0.2981	8.46
0.40	6	4	0.2400	6.95	0.3948	4.38
0.45	5.5	4.5	0.2698	6.19	...	...
0.50	5.0	5.0	0.2995	5.42	0.4922	2.52
0.55	4.5	5.5	0.3293	4.89	...	...
0.60	4.0	6.0	0.3589	4.04	0.5907	1.89
0.65	3.5	6.5	0.3890	3.86	...	...
0.70	3.0	7.0	0.4185	3.02	0.6894	1.31
0.75	2.5	7.5	0.4485	2.69	...	...
0.80	2.0	8.0	0.4784	2.20	0.7883	0.84
0.90	1.0	9.0	0.5358	1.18	0.8872	0.35

N.B. The ionisation constant of formic acid at 26°.30° has been taken as $K_a=1.77 \times 10^{-4}$ ("The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions" by Harned and Owen, 2nd. Ed., p. 580).

*These data could not be shown in Fig. 4.

**The values of ϕ_{PbFor^+} for mixtures corresponding to $1-x=0.1$ for both sets of parent solutions calculated by eq. (5), Part I (*loc. cit.*), are small but negative and this indicates that $\phi_{\text{PbFor}^+}=0$ or negligible at the given dilution.

The results of ϕ_{H} measurements for mixtures of two sets of equimolecular parent solutions of lead nitrate and propionic acid, one set having concentration $C=0.5M$ and another set $C=0.2M$, have been shown in Table I. The curves I and II in Fig. 1 represent the $Y-x$ plots from the data in Table I for $C=0.5M$ and that for $C=0.2M$ respectively. The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' for the solution mixtures used in this work have been obtained in the same way as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and these values have been shown in Table II. As in the previous case of lead acetate complex, the plot of ' K ' against ' μ ' obtained from Table II yields a smooth curve which has not been used to determine the value of ' K ' by extrapolation. In Fig. 2 the graph $\phi K (= -\log K)$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ from Table II gives a straight line curve which on extrapolation to $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ gives the value of ϕK corresponding to the true thermodynamic constant ' K '. These values of ϕK and ' K ' at $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ are 2.34 and 4.57×10^{-3} at 28.30° respectively.

The results of ϕ_{H} measurements for mixtures of two sets of equimolecular parent solutions of lead nitrate and formic acid, one having concentration $C=0.2$ and another set $C=0.33$, have been shown in Table III. The values of ' Y ' against the corresponding values of ' x ' from Table III, for mixtures of lead nitrate and formic acid solutions, both being at concentration $C=0.2M$ have been graphically represented by curve I, and those for both parent solutions at concentration $C=0.33M$ by curve II, in Fig. 3. The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' for the solution mixtures, studied in the present work, have been

obtained by following the same procedure as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) of this series, and these are shown in Table IV. As in the previous case (vide Part I), the plot of 'K' against ' μ ' from Table IV yields a smooth curve, which has not been used to evaluate the value of 'K' by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. In Fig. 4 the graph $pK (= -\log K)$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ from Table IV gives a straight line curve which on extrapolation to $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ gives the value of pK corresponding to the true thermodynamic constant K . These values of pK and K at $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ are 0.74 and 182.0×10^{-3} at $26^\circ - 30^\circ$ respectively.

DISCUSSION

There appears to be no previous work on the determination of the dissociation constants of lead formate. Lead formate dissociates in two steps, viz.,

The value of K found here is really the value of K_2 , the dissociation constant for the second step. The value of K_2 is sufficiently large and the value of K_1 is expected to be even larger so that the first step dissociation may be regarded as nearly complete. The values of ' c_{PbFor^+} ' and ' $c_{\text{Pb}^{2+}}$ ' even in dilute solution mixtures of lead formate and nitric acid, are therefore expected to be large, so that the ionic strengths of the solution mixtures are expected to be high. Under such circumstances the Bjerrum equation for the formation function, which is essentially stoichiometric, cannot be applied with the assumption that $c_{\text{For}^-} \approx a_{\text{For}^-}$, in evaluating the preliminary values of k_1 and k_2 , the classical mass action constants necessary for calculating the approximate ionic strengths. Also, the "Debye-Hückel limiting law" becomes inapplicable, and hence, the values of f_1 and f_2 calculated therefrom will have large errors; moreover, in the calculation of the ionic strength, it will not be correct to make the necessary assumptions that $c_{\text{H}^+} \approx a_{\text{H}^+}$ and $c_{\text{For}^-} \approx a_{\text{For}^-}$. Hence, the value of K_1 has not been determined in case of lead formate by following the same method as in the case of "lead acetate complexes" to be discussed in Part III of this series.

Critical comments on the previous work on the complex formation between lead and propionate ions, as also on the present work will be made in Part III of this series.

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